

ADMM-BASED TRAINING FOR SPIKING NEURAL NETWORKS

Giovanni Perin^{*†} Cesare Bidini[‡] Riccardo Mazzieri[†] Michele Rossi^{†‡}

^{*} Department of Information Engineering, University of Brescia, Brescia, Italy

[†] Department of Information Engineering, University of Padova, Padova, Italy

[‡] Department of Mathematics “Tullio Levi-Civita”, University of Padova, Padova, Italy

Email: giovanni.perin@unibs.it, cesare.bidini@studenti.unipd.it,
riccardo.mazzieri@phd.unipd.it, michele.rossi@unipd.it

ABSTRACT

In recent years, spiking neural networks (SNNs) have gained momentum due to their high potential in time-series processing combined with minimal energy consumption. However, they still lack a dedicated and efficient training algorithm. The popular backpropagation with surrogate gradients, adapted from stochastic gradient descent (SGD)-derived algorithms, has several drawbacks when used as an optimizer for SNNs. Specifically, it suffers from low scalability and numerical imprecision. In this paper, we propose a novel SNN training method based on the alternating direction method of multipliers (ADMM). Our ADMM-based training aims to solve the problem of the SNN step function’s non-differentiability. We formulate the problem, derive closed-form updates, and empirically show the optimizer’s convergence properties, great potential, and possible new research directions to improve the method in a simulated proof-of-concept.

Index Terms— ADMM, spiking neural networks, NNs optimizers, gradient-free optimization, model-based learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Spiking neural networks (SNNs) adopt a neural architecture that closely mimics how the human brain works as an asynchronous, event-based dynamic system. They are especially interesting because they process the input over time, enabling real-time signal processing and inference. Moreover, they show three orders of magnitude of improvement in the energy-delay product (EDP) when running on dedicated hardware, being thus characterized by a great energy efficiency [1]. However, a dedicated training algorithm for SNNs has not yet been developed, and the methods used so far for their supervised training are adaptations of those used for traditional NNs [2]. Unfortunately, these training methods, and particularly the popular surrogate gradient algorithm [3], are unable to adapt to the dynamics of SNNs. Specifically, methods derived from the stochastic gradient descent

(SGD) replace the SNN spike step function with a continuous approximation during the backward pass, to enable the computation of its derivative. This leads to scalability issues concerning the addition of multiple layers and to the vanishing gradient problem as networks grow deeper.

In this work, we propose a new optimizer specifically tailored for SNNs based on the alternating direction method of multipliers (ADMM) [4]. We first formulate the learning task as an optimization problem having the target training loss as its cost function, and define the SNN neuronal dynamics as the optimization constraints. Our approach is *model-based*, as we optimize a model of the SNN where not only the network weights are learnable (optimized) variables, but also the state variables of the SNN themselves (membrane potentials and spikes). Hence, we solve the problem by deriving closed-form updates for the involved variables, with a dedicated subroutine to optimally handle the SNN step (activation) function. We underline that this approach is completely different from SGD-derived optimizers, where a forward pass of the data is needed to estimate the value of the loss and the gradient direction before performing an optimization step.

In summary, the contributions of this work are: i) a new optimizer based on the ADMM thought specifically for SNNs is proposed, ii) the optimization problem is relaxed, making it treatable, and closed-form iterative updates with a solid mathematical theory are derived, iii) a subroutine to optimally handle the presence of the SNN Heaviside step function is developed, and iv) a proof-of-concept through numerical simulations to show the potential of the training algorithm is presented. Improvements to the proposed ADMM-based technique are possible and should be pursued to make the method scalable to very large and complex architectures. Such promising directions are discussed in Sect. 6.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1. SNNs and training algorithms

SNNs offer a promising energy-efficient alternative to traditional artificial NNs through sparse, event-driven, and asyn-

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chronous computation. However, their non-differentiable spike dynamics pose a major challenge for their training.

The surrogate gradient method [3] is currently the dominant approach for training SNNs. It bypasses the spike function’s discontinuity by introducing a smooth, differentiable surrogate gradient during the backward pass, enabling the application of the backpropagation through time (BPTT) algorithm. Despite its empirical success, this technique comes with several drawbacks: it requires additional state variables and memory, introduces approximation errors that degrade performance, and is also susceptible to vanishing or exploding gradients, as the number of NN layers grows.

Complementary to gradient-based methods, biologically plausible, gradient-free “Hebbian” learning rules have historically received attention in the neuroscience literature. A notable example is spike-timing-dependent plasticity (STDP), a local and biologically inspired learning approach, showing promising results for unsupervised learning and feature extraction [5]. However, STDP struggles with scalability and accuracy in complex tasks and requires extensive hyperparameter tuning. More recently, forward-only learning algorithms [6, 7, 8] aim to bypass the need for backward gradient computation altogether by integrating learning directly during the forward pass. However, these approaches lack a strong theoretical underpinning, are not yet scalable to deep architectures, and are not competitive with gradient-based alternatives. Additionally, very few explore their use with SNNs and mainly focus on training traditional neural networks.

Altogether, existing approaches entail trade-offs between biological plausibility, learning effectiveness, and hardware efficiency. This motivates the increasing research interest in alternative training paradigms beyond backpropagation, specifically tailored to the dynamics of SNNs.

2.2. Gradient-free training with the ADMM

The use of dual methods and especially the ADMM [4] to develop gradient-free optimizers for NNs is rooted in the seminal paper [9], where the authors show a model-based optimization formulation of a feed-forward NN. The proposed alternating direction solution can be seen as a split Bregman iteration or an inexact formulation of the ADMM. In recent years, the approach gained momentum and has been improved with relaxed approaches to non-convex constraints and a computationally cheap estimation of the pseudoinverse matrix, making the algorithm faster and more efficient [10, 11, 12]. Some of these works also prove the convergence of the approach to a stable minimizer. Notably, in [13] the authors integrate the recent advances with Anderson acceleration, making the ADMM significantly faster and outperforming, among others, advanced SGD-based approaches like Adam and RM-Sprop. In recent years, alternatives to gradient-based methods have also been investigated for recurrent NNs (RNNs) [14, 15, 16], also using the ADMM. For the first time, in this paper, we apply a formulation similar to [9] to the neuronal dy-

namics of SNNs, which are particular in many aspects (see Sect. 3). To the best of our knowledge, we are the first to propose a gradient-free optimizer specifically tailored for SNNs and based on the ADMM optimization algorithm.

3. OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM FORMULATION

Throughout the paper, the layer and time indices will be denoted by $l = 1, \dots, L$ and $t = 1, \dots, T$, respectively, M denotes the number of samples of the dataset (batch) and n_l the number of neurons at layer l . The training optimizer is formulated in this section as a model-based optimization problem. Specifically, three sets of optimization variables are defined, namely, i) the model parameters (weights) for each layer $\mathbf{W} = \{W_l\}$, where W_l has dimension $n_{l-1} \times n_l$ (and \mathbf{W} has dimension $\sum_{l=1}^L n_{l-1} \times n_l$, where n_0 refers to the number of input neurons); ii) the membrane potentials (pre-activations) for each layer and time $\mathbf{z} = \{z_{l,t}\}$, where each $z_{l,t}$ has dimension $n_l \times M$ (and \mathbf{z} has dimension $T \times M \times \sum_{l=1}^L n_l$); and iii) the spikes (post-activations) for each layer and time $\mathbf{a} = \{a_{l,t}\}$, where again each $a_{l,t}$ has dimension $n_l \times M$ (and \mathbf{a} has dimension $T \times M \times \sum_{l=1}^{L-1} n_l$, as the output layer does not have an activation). The objective function is the target loss. We assume that it depends on the membrane potentials of the last layer at the last time index T and on the dataset labels y as $\ell(z_{L,T}, y)$. The SNN’s dynamics are modeled through the constraints relating the optimization variables. This translates to the optimization problem

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{a}} \quad & \ell(z_{L,T}, y) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & z_{l,1} = W_l a_{l-1,1} \\ & z_{l,t} = \delta z_{l,t-1} + W_l a_{l-1,t} - \vartheta a_{l,t-1} \\ & z_{L,t} = \delta z_{L,t-1} + W_L a_{L-1,t} \\ & a_{l,t} = H_\vartheta(z_{l,t}), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $a_{0,t}$ are the input training data (M samples). The first constraint models the first time step of every layer, which is an equation similar to the dynamics of a common feed-forward NN: the input is multiplied by the weights matrix to obtain the output. The second constraint encodes the neuronal dynamics for the following time steps at every layer except the last one: the coefficient δ is the exponential decay factor for the membrane potential, representing the neuron’s memory concerning the previous instant, while ϑ is the firing threshold. If a neuron at layer l fires at time t , we have $a_{l,t} = 1$ and the membrane potential loses a voltage equal to ϑ (otherwise $a_{l,t} = 0$). The third constraint expresses the dynamics of the last layer, where firing and the reset mechanism are disabled. The fourth constraint is the relation between membrane potentials and spikes: a neuron emits a spike when the potential exceeds the threshold ϑ . Note that this can be interpreted computationally as the activation function of the SNN: a Heaviside step function centered in ϑ (and denoted here by H_ϑ). A pictorial representation of the model is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Graphical representation of the SNN model used for the problem formulation in this paper.

3.1. Problem relaxation

Due to the non-convexity of the problem constraints, a relaxed version of problem (1) is derived, where the constraints are added to the objective function as penalties. Following the original approach in [9] and the papers that originated from it, we keep an exact constraint on the dynamics of the last membrane potential. The (relaxed) augmented Lagrangian [4] associated with problem (1) is

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L}_{\rho,\sigma}(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{a}, \lambda) &= \ell(z_{L,T}, y) + \frac{\rho}{2} \sum_{l=1}^L \|z_{l,1} - W_l a_{l-1,1}\|^2 \\
&+ \frac{\rho}{2} \sum_{l=1}^{L-1} \sum_{t=2}^T \|z_{l,t} - \delta z_{l,t-1} - W_l a_{l-1,t} + \vartheta a_{l,t}\|^2 \\
&+ \frac{\rho}{2} \sum_{t=2}^T \|z_{L,t} - \delta z_{L,t-1} - W_L a_{L-1,t}\|^2 \\
&+ \frac{\sigma}{2} \sum_{l=1}^{L-1} \sum_{t=1}^T \|a_{l,t} - H_{\vartheta}(z_{l,t})\|^2 \\
&+ \langle z_{L,T} - \delta z_{L,T-1} - W_L a_{L-1,T}, \lambda \rangle,
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where λ is a Lagrange multiplier and ρ and σ are parameters tuning the relative weight of the soft constraints concerning the cost function. Intuitively, the constraint for the last membrane potential must be kept because the presence of the objective function adds a drift on the quadratic penalty minimizer. For all the other variables, instead, the sole optimization term is the soft penalty. Therefore, upon convergence, the optimized value of the variables will satisfy the constraints.

4. ADMM-BASED SOLUTION

In this section, we tackle the solution to the relaxed version of the problem via the augmented Lagrangian of Eq. (2), using an alternating direction optimization along the three di-

rections defined by the three sets of optimization variables, plus the dual variable (Lagrange multiplier) update. Without loss of generality, in this work, for the loss function, we use the mean squared error (MSE) between the last membrane potential and the target label, i.e.,

$$\ell(z_{L,T}, y) = \|z_{L,T} - y\|^2. \tag{3}$$

This choice is convenient as it leads to a closed-form update. However, closed-form updates can be obtained for many other valid loss functions, and the method can be used even by retrieving the solution to subproblems via numerical solvers when a closed-form solution is not available.

We observe that by minimizing for each variable separately while considering the others as fixed parameters, the Lagrangian in Eq. (2) is a convex function. Specifically, each ADMM update solves an unconstrained quadratic program (least squares). This ensures that every update has a simple closed-form solution, which can be easily computed via matrix multiplications (and efficiently implemented on GPUs). Next, we use $\mathbb{1}(\cdot)$ as the indicator function, e.g., $\mathbb{1}(t < T)$ denotes all time steps smaller than T .

4.1. Weights update

We conveniently define the auxiliary vectors $x_l = [z_{l,1}, z_{l,2} - \delta z_{l,1} + \vartheta a_{l,1}, \dots, z_{l,T} - \delta z_{l,T-1} + \vartheta a_{l,T-1}]$, $l = 1, \dots, L-1$, and $x_L = [z_{L,1}, z_{L,2} - \delta z_{L,1}, \dots, z_{L,T} - \delta z_{L,T-1}]$. By setting to zero the partial derivatives, the following updates for the weights variables are obtained, as the solution of a linear regression:

$$\begin{aligned}
W_l &= \left(\sum_{t=1}^T x_{l,t} a_{l-1,t}^\top \right) \left(\sum_{t=1}^T a_{l-1,t} a_{l-1,t}^\top \right)^{-1} \quad l \neq L, \tag{4} \\
W_L &= \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \lambda a_{L-1,T}^\top + \sum_{t=1}^T x_{L,t} a_{L-1,t}^\top \right) \\
&\cdot \left(\sum_{t=1}^T a_{L-1,t} a_{L-1,t}^\top \right)^{-1}. \tag{5}
\end{aligned}$$

4.2. Pre-activations update

By minimizing the direction associated with the membrane potential variables $z_{l,t}$ and by momentarily ignoring the presence of the non-differentiable activation function H_{ϑ} , we find

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{l,t} &= \frac{q_{l,t} + \delta(r_{l,t+1} + \vartheta a_{l,t}) \mathbb{1}(t < T)}{1 + \delta^2 \mathbb{1}(t < T)} \quad l \neq L, \tag{6} \\
z_{L,t} &= \frac{\rho s_{L,t} + \rho \delta r_{L,t+1} \mathbb{1}(t < T)}{\rho + \rho \delta^2 \mathbb{1}(t < T) + 2 \mathbb{1}(t = T)} + \\
&+ \frac{(2y - \lambda) \mathbb{1}(t = T) + \delta \lambda \mathbb{1}(t = T - 1)}{\rho + \rho \delta^2 \mathbb{1}(t < T) + 2 \mathbb{1}(t = T)}, \tag{7}
\end{aligned}$$

where for convenience we have defined the auxiliary vectors $p_l = W_l [a_{l-1,1}, \dots, a_{l-1,T}]$, $s_l = p_l + \delta [0, z_{l,1}, \dots, z_{l,T-1}]$, $q_l = s_l - \vartheta [0, a_{l,1}, \dots, a_{l,T-1}]$, and $r_l = -p_l + z_l$.

Now, we observe that, for $l \neq L$, the terms $\|a_{l,t} - H_\vartheta(z_{l,t})\|^2$ have to be additionally considered (see Eq. (2)). The non-differentiability of H_ϑ requires a dedicated subroutine that tests the value of the objective function when H_ϑ is active/inactive (if logic). Specifically, since each entry contributes to the Lagrangian cost in an additive and separable way, we evaluate if commuting the Heaviside step yields a better solution entry-wise (see Algorithm 1). In Line 4 the algorithm checks whether $z_{l,t}^{n_l,m} > \vartheta$, causing a spike. However, lowering it below the threshold to prevent firing would yield a better solution, hence we set $z_{l,t}^{n_l,m}$ to the highest possible value not surpassing the threshold (i.e., ϑ itself), as it is the best solution according to the cost function (a Euclidean norm). The dual case appears in Line 6, where the membrane potential $z_{l,t}^{n_l,m}$ is below the threshold ϑ and generating a spike would yield a better solution. Therefore, the potential is set slightly above the threshold ϑ , using a user-defined and small parameter $\varepsilon > 0$.

Algorithm 1 z minimizer subroutine

```

1: procedure Z_MINIMIZER( $z$ )
2:   for each entry of  $z$  do
3:     if  $z_{l,t}^{n_l,m} > \vartheta$  &  $\text{cost}(\vartheta) \leq \text{cost}(z_{l,t}^{n_l,m})$  then
4:        $z_{l,t}^{n_l,m} \leftarrow \vartheta$ 
5:     else if  $z_{l,t}^{n_l,m} \leq \vartheta$  &  $\text{cost}(\vartheta + \varepsilon) < \text{cost}(z_{l,t}^{n_l,m})$ 
6:       then
7:          $z_{l,t}^{n_l,m} \leftarrow \vartheta + \varepsilon$ 
8:       end if
9:     end for
10:  end procedure

```

4.3. Post-activations update

For the post-activations (i.e., the spikes) update, we note that this variable only exists up to and including layer $l = L - 1$, as layer L does not have an activation function. For compactness, we define the auxiliary vectors $u_l = [z_{l,1}, z_{l,2} - \delta z_{l,1}, \dots, z_{l,T} - \delta z_{l,T-1}]$, $v_l = u_l + \vartheta[0, a_{l,1}, \dots, a_{l,T-1}]$, and $w_l = u_l - W_l[a_{l-1,1}, \dots, a_{l-1,T}]$. The spikes $a_{l,t}$ are obtained as

$$a_{l,t} = (\rho W_{l+1}^\top W_{l+1} + (\sigma + \rho \vartheta^2 \mathbb{1}(t < T))I)^{-1} \cdot (\rho W_{l+1}^\top v_{l+1,t} - \rho \vartheta w_{l,t+1} \mathbb{1}(t < T) + \sigma H_\vartheta(z_{l,t})),$$

$$l \neq L - 1, \quad (8)$$

$$a_{L-1,t} = (\rho W_L^\top W_L + (\sigma + \rho \vartheta^2 \mathbb{1}(t < T))I)^{-1} (W_L^\top (\rho u_{L,t} + \lambda \mathbb{1}(t = T)) - \rho \vartheta w_{L-1,t+1} \mathbb{1}(t < T) + \sigma H_\vartheta(z_{l,t})). \quad (9)$$

Neurons' spikes are physically constrained to be binary variables: either a neuron fires ($a_{l,t} = 1$) or it does not ($a_{l,t} = 0$). However, projecting the value retrieved in the binary space produces instability for the ADMM iterations towards convergence, as the values might often change abruptly. Therefore, we instead adopt a clipping procedure enforcing $0 \leq a_{l,t} \leq 1$ (i.e., we set $a_{l,t} = \min(\max(0, a_{l,t}), 1)$).

Table 1: Parameters used for the numerical simulations.

Parameter	Value
Number of time steps T	150
Neurons per layer n_l	512
Number of classes n_c	10
Optimization parameters $(\rho, \sigma, \delta, \vartheta)$	(1, 0.1, 0.95, 1)
(Total, warming) ADMM iterations	(1000, 300)
Number of training samples M	200

4.4. Training algorithm

The full training algorithm using the z minimizer subroutine explained in Algorithm 1 is summarized in Algorithm 2. Algorithm 2 represents a single ADMM iteration, which must be repeated until a convergence criterion is met [4].

Algorithm 2 ADMM optimizer for SNNs

```

1: for  $l = 1, \dots, L - 1$  do
2:   Update the weights  $W_l$  with Eq. (4)
3:   for  $t = 1, \dots, T$  do
4:     Update the pre-activations  $z_{l,t}$  with Eq. (6)
5:      $z_{l,t} \leftarrow \text{z\_minimizer}(z_{l,t})$ 
6:     if  $l < L - 1$  then
7:       Update the post-activations  $a_{l,t}$  with Eq. (8)
8:     else
9:       Update the post-activations  $a_{L-1,t}$  with Eq. (9)
10:    end if
11:     $a_{l,t} \leftarrow \min(\max(0, a_{l,t}), 1)$ 
12:  end for
13: end for
14: Update the weights  $W_L$  with Eq. (5)
15: for  $t = 1, \dots, T$  do
16:   Update the pre-activations  $z_{L,t}$  with Eq. (7)
17: end for
18:  $\lambda \leftarrow \lambda + \rho(z_{L,T} - \delta z_{L,T-1} - W_L a_{L-1,T})$ 

```

5. NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

The simulations were implemented in Python using PyTorch tensors¹ in full compatibility with the existing `snnTorch` package². In these simulations, whose settings are summarized in Tab. 1, we used the neuromorphic dataset N-MNIST. We also adopted a *stochastic ADMM* approach where the order of the updates was chosen randomly for the layers and the time steps, as this procedure yielded better results.

In Fig. 2, the training accuracy reached for 1,000 ADMM iterations is shown varying the number of hidden layers. As can be seen, the framework is currently solid in solving the classification task with a single hidden layer (around 95% accuracy), but the performance decreases with an increasing number of hidden layers (around 70% accuracy for two hidden layers and progressively lower). The reason is better investigated in the convergence study shown in Figs. 3 and 4,

¹The code is available at https://anonymous.4open.science/r/SNN_ADMM_Optimizer-3116/admm_snn.py

²<https://snnTorch.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Fig. 2: Train accuracy obtained in 1,000 ADMM iterations varying the number of hidden layers.

Fig. 3: Objective functions of the ADMM optimization: relaxed Lagrangian (left) and target loss function (right). Training of the SNN with two hidden layers.

evaluated for the training of the SNN with two hidden layers.

Figure 3a shows the relaxed Lagrangian value during training. From this plot, we see that, after a quick and significant decrease in the first 100 iterations, the Lagrangian reaches a plateau after iteration 200. Hence, it might seem that a stable minimizer has been found; however, by observing the target loss function (Fig. 3b), we see that the value is still decreasing and would continue the trend after iteration 1,000. We obtain similar conclusions for the residuals shown in Fig. 4. Specifically, we observe that the primal residuals (Fig. 4a) suddenly drop to 10^{-6} when the Lagrange multiplier is activated, showing the efficacy of the dual approach. However, the residuals of the soft constraints for the variables z (Fig. 4b) and α (Fig. 4c) decrease at a slower pace: This causes a mismatch between the optimization and the prediction at inference since the neuronal dynamics are not respected with enough numerical precision. The effect is more evident as the number of layers and time steps increases. Allowing the soft constraints to further reduce their values with more training iterations would improve the performance.

6. DISCUSSION

The current approach has potential and yet great room for improvement. We note that, unlike classic NNs, SNNs have a time dimension that adds a factor of the order of 10^3 in the number of variables, making the problem more complex

Fig. 4: Constraint residuals. Exact constraint primal residual of the last membrane potential (left), norm of the soft constraints relative to the membrane potential dynamics per layer (middle), and norm of the soft constraints relative to the neurons' spikes per layer (right). Training of the SNN with two hidden layers.

to tackle. Nonetheless, the ADMM is known for handling problems with up to $\sim 10^9$ variables when several empirical techniques are combined with the standard framework [4], as the convergence might be extremely sensitive to hyperparameters, as we also observed for this specific problem. For instance, as also done in other works, an adaptive value for ρ and σ across iterations might speed up the convergence of the soft constraints, as well as the addition of Anderson acceleration [13]. These implementations would also make the optimizer more resistant to scalability for the number of layers and time steps.

However, we demonstrated that this first approach already handles the presence of the non-differentiability of the Heaviside step well, as the dedicated subroutine developed produces a stable (although slow) convergence towards the minimizer, representing a significant novelty concerning the commonly used surrogate gradient methods. We also note that the approach can be extended to convolutional SNNs by modifying the soft constraints relative to the membrane potential dynamics. In this case, the multiplication between the weight matrix W_l and the spikes $a_{l-1,t}$ would be replaced by a correlation operation, which is still linear and can be handled by the ADMM. It is also important to mention that, like in previous approaches derived from [9], the presented training algorithm is suitable for processing the entire dataset, instead of processing small batches in series and performing many (imprecise) backpropagation steps with a coarse estimation of the gradient, like SGD-based optimizers do. In sharp contrast, with the ADMM, fewer optimal subproblems, more computationally expensive, are executed at each iteration, spanning, in principle, the whole dataset. However, the available memory might be a bottleneck in this situation. The solution to this is the consideration that the variables $z_{l,t}$ and $a_{l,t}$ are independent sample-wise: hence, several CPUs and/or GPUs can process different subsets of the dataset in parallel. However, the weights update requires integrating the information with

the update

$$W_l = \left(\sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^T x_{l,t}^n a_{l-1,t}^{n\top} \right) \left(\sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^T a_{l-1,t}^n a_{l-1,t}^{n\top} \right)^{-1}, \quad (10)$$

where n is the worker (similarly, batch) index. This directly enables federated learning (FL), where the parameter server (PS) computes the reduction update in Eq. (10) while the clients keep a portion of the dataset and updates the variables $z_{l,t}^n$ and $a_{l,t}^n$ locally and privately.

7. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this work, we presented a first formulation of an ADMM optimizer specifically tailored for SNNs. The iterative solution only uses closed-form updates and a subroutine with if-else logic to optimally treat the presence of the non-differentiable Heaviside step function. Notably, the proposed procedure solves the issue of the poor approximation of the gradient used in surrogate gradient methods. With this work, we aim to start a new research line on SNN optimizers: The proposed method has great potential and significant room for improvement and possible extensions.

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